

The relative standard deviation was observed to be $\pm 0.95\%$ in 38 determinations. Estimation of 40 mg/ml of uranium (VI) was possible in the presence of 0.2 mg of Ag(I), Ti(I), Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Be(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Bi(III), Ce(III), In (III), Zr (IV), V(V), W(VI) or Mo(VI) and 0.15 mg of Pb(II), Al(III), Th(IV) or Cr(VI) with relative error less than $\pm 2\%$ provided Mg-EDTA was used as the masking agent. Uranium content of several ores containing U_3O_8 between 2.29 to 24.70% was determined with a relative error within $\pm 1\%$.

Organic complexing acids, e.g. thioglycolic, tartaric, oxalic, citric and ascorbic acids as well as triethanolamine and fluoride interfered in the determination of uranium(VI).

The metal to ligand ratio of the complex was found to be 1 : 2².

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Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of Some Lanthanides with Methoxy Substituted Benzoic Acids

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MAY and Jones¹ have studied the interaction of Cu^{2+} with 4-methoxy benzoic acid in 50% dioxane-water medium. There is however no reference in literature on the work presented in this paper.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of Analar grade obtained either from Fluka (Switzerland) or E. Merck (India). Dioxane (E. Merck) was purified by the method described by Vogel². All the solutions

were prepared in water, distilled in an all glass apparatus.

The rare earth oxides obtained from the Bhaba Atomic Research Centre Bombay, (purity 99.9%) were converted to respective perchlorates and used in order to avoid the possibility of complex formation of metal ions with the anions. Their concentrations in solutions were determined by their estimation as oxalates.

An Elico pH meter model LI10 in conjunction with an Elico standard general purpose glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode was used for the measurement of pH during the potentiometric titrations. The meter could read pH accurate to ± 0.02 pH unit. It was calibrated using standard solution prepared from buffer tablets supplied by BDH London.

Calvin-Bjerrum titration: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titrations of carbonate free solutions of i) free $HClO_4$ ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) ii) free $HClO_4$ ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand ($2 \times 10^{-3}M$) and iii) free $HClO_4$ ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand ($2 \times 10^{-3}M$) + metal ($4 \times 10^{-4}M$) against standard sodium hydroxide 0.4M at 30°. The ionic strength was maintained constant by addition of appropriate amount of $NaClO_4$ solution. An inert atmosphere was maintained inside the titration cell by bubbling nitrogen gas presaturated with solvent. The glass electrode was calibrated in mixed solvent (76% v/v dioxane-water medium) by method given by Van Uitert and Haas³.

Results and Discussion

The pK values of methoxy substituted benzoic acids in 76% dioxane-water v/v medium containing 0.1M $NaClO_4$ ionic strength, have been reported in our earlier communication.⁴ These are listed in Table 1 for ready reference.

The complex formation of lanthanide ions with different ligands was indicated by considerable displacement along the volume axis of metal complex titration curve with the respect to the reagent curve, at a pH value less than that of the hydrolysis of the lanthanide ion. The possibility of metal ion hydrolysis under experimental conditions was therefore,

TABLE-1 THERMODYNAMIC PROTON LIGAND AND METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF RARE EARTH CHELATES OF METHOXY SUBSTITUTED BENZOIC ACIDS

Ligand	Temp. = 30° ± 0.1° ; H ⁺	$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ;$			Medium 76% : v/v. dioxane-water.			
		La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Bb ³⁺
2-methoxy B. A.	8.79	6.89	6.88	6.87	6.48	5.79	7.59	6.99
4-methoxy B. A.	9.11	6.80	7.22	6.86	6.21	6.03	7.51	6.93
2,3-dimethoxy B. A.	8.37	6.33	6.89	6.94	5.89	5.23	7.35	5.92
2,4-dimethoxy B. A.	9.29	7.10	7.63	7.32	6.88	5.83	7.78	7.15
2,6-dimethoxy B. A.	8.49	6.19	6.42	6.53	6.00	5.67	7.01	6.29
2,4,5-trimethoxy B. A.	9.33	7.30	7.16	7.33	6.62	5.81	7.72	7.66
2,4,6-trimethoxy B. A.	8.85	6.71	7.08	6.84	5.97	5.39	7.14	6.15

NOTES

assumed to be negligible. The solutions employed were so dilute that the formation of any polynuclear species could be ignored.

The $\log K_1$ values were calculated by using expression $\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} = \log K_1 - pL$ and plotting a graph for $\bar{n}$ values between 0.2 to 0.8. The $\log K_1$ values obtained are presented in Table 1.

In the systems studied only 1 : 1 complexes were formed. The possibility of 1 : 2 complexes cannot be considered since $\bar{n}$ values higher than 1 were erratic and fell near the pH of hydrolysis.

*log K = a.pK + b relation*⁵ : In the rare earth chelates of substituted methoxy benzoic acids the plots of $\log K$ vs pK gave straight line relationship in every case. The slopes lie between 0.85 and 0.95. The almost identical magnitude of the slopes for the various lanthanide chelates of methoxy substituted benzoic acids, indicates similar nature of the chelates and the mode of dissociation of different ligands.⁶⁻⁸

Jones *et al*⁹ have suggested on the basis of purely electrostatic model that the slope value will increase with increasing cationic charge and decreasing distance of separation (equal to the radius of cation plus a constant). The slope values for Cx^{2+} methoxy benzoic acid complexes by present authors was 0.45¹⁰. The higher charge on rare earth cations is expected to give a higher value of slope. Hence the slope values for rare earth cations are higher than that of the Cu^{2+} .

As is often the case a break in regular change of properties of rare earth occurs at gadolinium. It has been observed that the Gd^{3+} chelates of all the ligands have lower $\log K$ values as compared to those of Sm^{3+} and Dy^{3+} . Linear discontinuity is found in a plot of $\log K$ vs e^2/r .

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Synthesis of Cyclohepta [b] Thiophen Derivatives

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IN connection with our investigation in the fields of dehydrogenation¹ and desulphurization reactions, several cyclohepta [b] thiophen derivatives were needed. Here we report the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-one (7), 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6.6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta[b] thiophen (10) and their alkyl derivatives by an adaptation of the method developed earlier¹ in this laboratory, for the synthesis of benzene analogue of the above compounds. Recently synthesis and photochemical behaviour of cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-ones were reported by Jones and co-worker².

To synthesise the keto acid (1) we have studied the Friedel-Craft condensation of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic anhydride with thiophen under different experimental conditions (vide Table 1). Aluminium chloride and stannic chloride catalysed reactions gave some unidentified polymeric material containing sulphur. When BF_3 -etherate was used as a catalyst, no condensation product was isolated. The keto acid (1) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the pentanoic acid (4). The acid chloride of the reduced acid was cyclised using stannic chloride to give the cyclic ketone (7). Preparation of the acid chloride by oxalyl chloride method had improved the yield and quality of the cyclic product [vide experimental, compounds (10) and (11)]. The cyclic ketone was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the spiran (10).